

"SOCIAL-PHILOSOPHICAL FACTORS OF FORMATION OF ENGINEERING THINKING IN THE MINDS OF YOUNG STUDENTS"

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Abstract: The importance of pedagogic factors in shaping the worldview of students and young people, logical and engineering thinking is incomparable. Achieving the desired result by using independent thinking and intellectual abilities in students by forming logical thinking . In addition, the study of the methods of professional development of the individual provided the data analyzed because the possibilities of developing a professionally relevant mindset for future engineers are increasingly relevant.

Keywords: Engineering, STEM, pedagogical activity, intellectual, interactive method, problem solving, modularization, scientific, organic, systematic, vitality, deductive, inductive.

Engineers use science and mathematics to find practical solutions to problems.

Engineering is the application of science and mathematics to solve problems. Engineers figure out how things work and find practical uses for scientific discoveries. Scientists and inventors often receive awards for innovations that improve the human condition, but it is engineers who are important in bringing these innovations to the world.

Physicist Freeman Dyson wrote in his book *Disturbing the Universe* (Sloan Foundation, 1981) that "A good scientist is someone who has ideas of their own. A good engineer is someone who creates a design that works with just a few ideas. . can. There is no prima donna in engineering."

The history of engineering is part of the history of human civilization. The pyramids of Giza, Stonehenge, the Parthenon and the Eiffel Tower stand today as monuments to our engineering heritage. Today's engineers are not only building

giant structures like the International Space Station, but they are mapping the human genome and even smaller computer chips.

Engineering is one of the cornerstones of STEM education, an interdisciplinary curriculum designed to encourage students to learn about science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.

our respected first president I. A. Karimov noted, "We know very well how important the work of a teacher is in shaping the spiritual world of the new generation, the owners of new thinking, the young people who will replace us tomorrow. Because a teacher is not a class. "He is an honorable person who brings grace and wisdom into his room, but also showers kindness and teaches life to thousands of young souls." For this reason, today in higher educational institutions, our pedagogic teachers organize pedagogical activities consisting of organizational, motivational, educational thinking and control stages for students in order to form logical thinking in future pedagogues. Organization of the didactic process is an important and exciting process in our pedagogical activity. It is on the basis of cognitive processes that the professional consciousness, thinking, and worldview of future pedagogues are formed. At the same time, every pedagogical process organized by the pedagogue in the auditorium plays an exemplary role in the professional formation of future pedagogues. Let's look at pedagogical activity and its components. In pedagogical activity, the stage of educational thinking activity constitutes the "core" of the pedagogical process. At this stage, students' level of mastery can be divided into two types. These are: productive and unproductive. The difference between them is that in unproductive activity, a person uses the rules of action (algorithm) known to him, and no new information emerges in this process. It only re-develops the methods it has mastered before. It is formed on the basis of non-productive and reproductive methods. For example: getting to know the topic, speaking, having information. Today, reproductive methods are used in lectures and seminars in the student auditorium.

When performing a productive activity, the student always encounters novelty or new information (new objects, events, processes, methods of activity are created, both activities are performed independently or with the help of external influence. For example, an unproductive activity instruction (or (guide, dictionary, teacher) or on the basis of other sources of information about the rules for performing actions, i.e. without instructions, it is performed independently. Productive activity can also be performed under certain methodical instructions, but here the sequence of actions is carried out by means of methods that are updated on the spot, (only for a few) or unknown.

Taking into account the points stated above, the student's learning activities can be divided into the following four levels, which can solve any problems:

Level 1: action under the influence of external instruction. We tentatively call this activity the FAMILIARITY level.

Level 2: memory-based action. We call this the ALGORITHM level of activity.

Level 3: productive behavior in non-standard situations. We call this the HEURISTIC level of activity.

Level 4: productive activity exploring new aspects of educational activity. We call this the CREATIVE level of activity.

Raising the educational process to a higher level determines the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. The main purpose of the use of pedagogical technologies in the continuous education system is to raise the educational process to a creative level. Consequently. It is inextricably linked with the formation of students' worldview in the educational process. Worldview is formed on the basis of a set of ideas that arise during the educational process.

, which is an independent activity that has its own motive (power to act, spiritual need), goal, and methods . with the help of thinking, the conscious or unconscious aspects of things and events reflected in the human brain or psyche become clear.

Thinking itself is guided by research on this path. Thinking is a necessary part of influencing the other person who enters into communication, it is also the basis of knowing each other.

Experts dealing with the human psyche testify that one of the main conditions of the human thinking process - his desire to know the words of existence, his inner need - is a motive. Without it, a person cannot think. The joint work of those around the thinking person. It is formed and developed in mutual communication and cooperation.

Logical thinking is conscious, self-controlled thinking based on scientific theoretical foundations. According to Vygotsky, the absence of logic in thinking means the absence of independence and freedom in the process of thinking. Students develop independent thinking content based on logical thinking. Therefore, independent thinking is a mental activity that consists of solving problems and tasks in front of a person, relying on his knowledge and life experiences, with the help of various methods and tools, at the level of his intellectual capabilities.

The logical thinking process of students in higher educational institutions is influenced by the pedagogue's pedagogical skills and the subjects in the curriculum. They can be conditionally divided into two groups; subjects that form direct action skills and abilities, and more abstract subjects that compel mental, imaginative understanding. The more information available to students, the more varied and complementary, the more organized and logical their thinking becomes. Interdisciplinarity, their generalization, systematization, inductive, deductive approach play an important role in forming the logical thinking of future pedagogues. The high stage of the educational process is the development of independent knowledge skills and abilities based on the formation of students' internal need for knowledge. It is important to use modern pedagogical technologies, comprehensive conceptual approach to the content of education in forming the logical thinking of students. Identifying the philosophical basis of learning such educational content, moving from reproductive mastery to the creative stage,

connecting with life, directing mental activity to perform logical operations such as analysis, synthesis, creates a foundation for the birth of logical thought. Our pedagogues' explanation of the educational process based on logic, problematization of the educational process, modularization and other interactive methods relying on the principles of scientificity, organicity, systematicity, and vitality are the priority in finding the content of students' logical thinking.

In the process of education, directing the pedagogues to creative knowledge creates a basis for the formation of creative ideas in the mind of the individual, the superficial knowledge realizes the loss of creative knowledge, and the formation of an independent conscious attitude is knowledge.

Therefore, in the professional formation of future pedagogues in higher educational institutions, we should consider raising the educational process from reproductive education to productive level as a social necessity. Therefore, it is impossible to form the independent free thinking of students without forming a critical thinking of logic in the formation of the profession of our pedagogues.

To have unexpected results and solutions by forming divergent thinking in students, branching out in different ways, spreading in different directions at the same time, creating many solution options.

, it is desirable to focus on the activation of student cognitive processes - intuition, perception, memory, attention and thinking, and to effectively use advanced methods of education.

in technical fields is not effective enough. The dynamics of its development level was characterized by the fact that it does not remain the same throughout the years of student education .

References:

- 1 . Userbay , B. _ (9102). Independent education - student of knowledge basis . Turkish backpacks folklore , literary critic in uam of linguistics it's important issues : Khaltsaro conference , 1(1), 105-108.

2. Shaikhislamov, N. (2020). Proverb as an object of linguistic analysis. Increasing the innovative activity of young people, improving their spirituality and achievements in the field of science, 31-33.

3. Allaberdieva, K. (2019). The Main Neuropedagogic Possibilities Of Formation At Children Of Senior Preschool Age Of Creative Activity. European Journal Of Research And Reflection In Educational Sciences Vol, 7, 12.

4. Аллабердиева, К. Х. (2022). ИЖОДИЙ ФАОЛЛИКНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШГА ЙЎНАЛТИРИЛГАН ИНТЕГРАЦИЯЛАШГАН ТАЪЛИМ. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 1(5), 419-423.